

Neutrosophic Crisp β - Functions

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Abstract

The purpose of the present paper is to introduce and study the concept of β -continuous function and β -open function in neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. Finally, some characterizations concerning neutrosophic crisp functions are presented and one obtains several properties.

Keywords: Neutrosophic crisp β -continuous function, Neutrosophic crisp β -open function and Neutrosophic crisp β -closed function

1. Introduction

Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic components T, I, F which represent the membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership values respectively, where $]0, 1^+$ is non-standard unit interval. After the introduction of the neutrosophic crisp set concepts in [1-8] and after having given the fundamental definitions of neutrosophic crisp set operations. Some applications of neutrosophic theory can be found in [12-16]. We generalize the crisp functions to the notion of neutrosophic crisp set. Finally, we introduce the definitions of neutrosophic crisp β -continuous function and neutrosophic crisp β -open function, and we obtain several properties and some characterizations concerning the neutrosophic crisp topological space.

2. Preliminaries

We recollect some relevant basic preliminaries, and in particular, the work of Smarandache in [9-11]. Salama et al. [1-8] considered some possible definitions for basic concepts of the neutrosophic crisp set and its operations. We now improve some results by the following.

Definition 2.1 [4]

For any non-empty fixed set X , a neutrosophic crisp set (NC -set, for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, where A_1, A_2 and A_3 are subsets of X satisfying $A_1 \cap A_2 = \emptyset$, $A_1 \cap A_3 = \emptyset$ and $A_3 \cap A_2 = \emptyset$. Several relations and operations between NC -sets were defined in [3, 6, 8].

Definition 2.2 [3]

A neutrosophic crisp topology (NCT , for short) on a non-empty set X is a family Γ of neutrosophic crisp subsets of X satisfying the following axioms

- i) $\emptyset, X_N \in \Gamma$.
- ii) $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \Gamma$ for any A_1 and $A_2 \in \Gamma$.
- iii) $\cup A_j \in \Gamma$ for any $\{A_j: j \in J\} \subseteq \Gamma$.

In this case the pair (X, Γ) is called a neutrosophic crisp topological space ($NCTS$, for short) in X . The elements in Γ are called neutrosophic crisp open sets (NC -open sets for short) in X . A NC -set F is said to be neutrosophic crisp closed set (NC -closed set, for short) if and only if its complement F^c is a NC -open set.

Definition 2.3 [3]

Let (X, Γ) be a $NCTS$ and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ be a NC -set in X . Then the neutrosophic crisp closure of A ($NC(A)$ for short) and neutrosophic crisp interior ($NCint(A)$ for short) of A are defined by:

- (i) $NCcl(A) = \cap \{K: K \text{ is a } NC\text{-closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$
- (ii) $NCint(A) = \cup \{G: G \text{ is a } NC\text{-open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$,

It can be also shown that $NC(A)$ is a NC -closed set, and $NCint(A)$ is a NC -open set in X .

Definition 2.4 [1]

Let (X, Γ) be a $NCTS$ and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ be a NCS in X , then A is called:

- i) Neutrosophic crisp α -open set iff $A \subseteq NCi(NCcl(NCint(A)))$.
- ii) Neutrosophic crisp semi-open set iff $A \subseteq NC(NCint(A))$.
- iii) Neutrosophic crisp pre-open set iff $A \subseteq NCi(NCcl(A))$.
- iv) Neutrosophic crisp β -open set iff $A \subseteq (NCcl(NCi(NCcl(A))))$.

Definition 2.5 [1]

Let (X, Γ) be a $NCTS$ and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ be a NCS in X , and $f: X \rightarrow X$ then:

- 1) If f $NC\alpha$ -continuous $\Rightarrow$ inverse image of $NC\alpha$ open set is $NC\alpha$ -open set
- 2) If f $NCpre$ -continuous $\Rightarrow$ inverse image of $NCpre$ -open set is $NCpre$ -open set
- 3) If f $NCsemi$ -continuous $\Rightarrow$ inverse image of $NCsemi$ -open set is $NCsemi$ -open set
- 4) If f $NC\beta$ -continuous $\Rightarrow$ inverse image of $NC\beta$ -open set is $NC\beta$ -open set

Definition 2.6 [3]

- (a) If $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ is a NC -set in X , then the NC -image of A under f denoted by $f(A)$ is the a NC -set in Y defined by $f(A) = \langle f(A_1), f(A_2), f(A_3) \rangle$
- (b) If f is a bijective map then $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is a map defined such that: for any NC -set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ in Y , the NC -preimage of B , denoted by $f^{-1}(B)$ is a NC -set in X defined by $f^{-1}(B) = \langle f^{-1}(B_1), f^{-1}(B_2), f^{-1}(B_3) \rangle$.

Here we introduce the properties of NC -images and NC -preimages, some of which we shall frequently use in the following sections.

Corollary 2.1 [3]

Let $A = \{A_i: i \in J\}$ be NC -open sets in X , and $B = \{B_j: j \in K\}$ be NC -open sets in Y , and $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ a function. Then

- (i) $A_1 \subseteq A_2 \Leftrightarrow f(A_1) \subseteq f(A_2)$, $B_1 \subseteq B_2 \Leftrightarrow f^{-1}(B_1) \subseteq f^{-1}(B_2)$,
- (ii) $A \subseteq f^{-1}(f(A))$ and if f is injective, then $A_1 = f^{-1}(f(A_1))$.
- (iii) $f^{-1}(f(B)) \subseteq B$ and if f is injective, then $f^{-1}(f(B)) = B$.
- (iv) $f^{-1}(\cup B_i) = \cup f^{-1}(B_i)$, $f^{-1}(\cap B_i) \subseteq \cap f^{-1}(B_i)$,
- (v) $f(\cup A_i) = \cup f(A_i)$, $f(\cap A_i) \subseteq \cap f(A_i)$.
- (vi) $f^{-1}(Y_N) = X_N$, $f^{-1}(\Phi_N) = \Phi_N$,
- (vii) $f(\Phi_N) = \Phi_N$, $f(X_N) = Y_N$, if f is surjective.

3. Neutrosophic crisp β -continuous function

Definition 3.1

A function $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is said to be $NC\beta$ -continuous (briefly $NC\beta$ -cont) if the inverse image of each NC -open set in Y is $NC\beta$ -open in X .

It is clear that the class of $NC\beta$ -continuity contains each of classes NC -semiopen and NC -preopen the implication between them and other type of continuities are given by the following diagram.

The converses of these implication not hold, in general, as shown in the following example.

Example 3.1

Let $X=Y= \{a,b,c,d\}$ and let the NCT on X be indiscrete and on Y be discrete. The identity function $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is $NC\beta$ -continuous but not NC -semi continuous.

Example 3.2

Let $X=Y= \{a,b,c,d\}$ with NC -topologies $\Gamma_x = \{X_N, \Phi_N, A\}$, $\Gamma_y = \{Y_N, \Phi_N, D\}$ where
 $A = \{\{a,b\}, \{b,d\}, \{c\}\}$,
 $D = \{\{a,d\}, \{a,d\}, \{c\}\}$.

A function $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ which defined as

$f(a)=a, f(b)=c$ and $f(c)=b, f(d)=a$, is $NC\beta$ -cont. but not NC -pre cont.

The following theorem gives easy characterization of $NC\beta$ -continuity.

Theorem 3.3

Each $NC\beta$ -open set which is also NC semi-closed set is NC semi-open.

Proof. Let $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ be a $NC\beta$ -open set which is also $NC\beta$ -closed set then, $A \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCclA$ and $A \subseteq NCint\ NCclA$. Thus $NCint\ NCclA \subseteq A \subseteq NC(NCint\ NCclA)$. Therefore, $A = \langle A_{1,2}, A_3 \rangle$ is NC -semiopen.

Theorem 3.4

Let $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a function. The following statement are equivalent.

(i) f is $NC\beta$ -cont.

For each NC -set $x \in X$ and each NC -open set $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ containing $f(x)$, there exists a $NC\beta$ -open set $W = \langle W_1, W_2, W_3 \rangle \subseteq X$ containing x such that $f(W) \subseteq V$.

(ii) the inverse image of each NC -closed set in Y is $NC\beta$ -closed set in X .

(iii) $NCint NCcl NCi(f^{-1}(A)) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl(A))$.

(iv) $f(NCint NCcl NCint D) \subseteq NCcl(f(D))$. For each $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle \subseteq X$.

Proof. (i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii). Since $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ containing $f(x)$ is NC -open, then

$f^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$. NC -set $W = f^{-1}(V)$. which containing x , therefore $f(W) \subseteq V$.

(i) $\Leftarrow$ (ii). Let $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ be NC -open, and let $x \in f^{-1}(V)$, then $f(x) \in V$ and thus there exists $W_x \in NC\beta(x)$. such that $x \in W_x$ and $f(W_x) \subseteq V$. then $x \in W_x \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$, and so, $f^{-1}(V) = \cup W_x, x \in f^{-1}(V)$. but $\cup W_x \in NC\beta(x)$ By Theorem 2.5. hence $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq NC\beta(x)$. and therefore f is $NC\beta$ -cont.

(i) $\Rightarrow$ (iii). Let $F = \langle F_1, F_2, F_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ be NC -closed, $Y-F$ is NC -open, $f^{-1}(Y-F) \in NC\beta(x)$. i.e., $X-f^{-1}(F) \in NC\beta(x)$. then $f^{-1}(F) = \langle f^{-1}(F_1), f^{-1}(F_2), f^{-1}(F_3) \rangle$ is $NC\beta$ -closed set in X .

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (iv). Let $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$, then $f^{-1}(NCcl(A))$ is $NC\beta$ -closed set in X , i.e., $f^{-1}(NCcl(A)) \supseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(NCcl(A))) \supseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(A))$.

(iv) $\Rightarrow$ (v). Let $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle \subseteq X$, NC -set $A = f(D)$ in (iv), that $NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(f(D))) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl(f(D)))$, $NCint NCcl int(D) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl(f(D)))$, then $f(NCint NCcl NCint(D)) \subseteq (NCcl(f(D)))$.

(v) $\Rightarrow$ (i). Let $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ be a NC -open, $W = Y-V$ and $D = f^{-1}(W)$, by $f(NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(W))) \subseteq NCcl(f(f^{-1}(W))) \subseteq NCcl(W) = W$.

so, $NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(W)) \subseteq f^{-1}(W)$, i.e., $f^{-1}(W) = \langle f^{-1}(W_1), f^{-1}(W_2), f^{-1}(W_3) \rangle$ is $NC\beta$ -closed set in X , thus f is $NC\beta$ -cont.

Theorem 3. 5

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\beta$ -cont. and $NC\alpha$ -open function. Then the inverse image of any $NC\beta$ -open set in Y is $NC\beta$ -open set of X .

Proof. Let $W = \langle W_1, W_2, W_3 \rangle \in NC\beta(y)$, then $W \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl(W)$ and so, $f^{-1}(W) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl NCint NCcl(W)) \subseteq NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint NCcl(W)))$. because f is $NC\alpha$ -open and $NCint NCcl(W)$ is NC -preopen. Since f is $NC\beta$ -cont. $f^{-1}(W) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint NCcl(W))) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl(f^{-1}(NCcl NCint NCcl(W))) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl(f^{-1}(W)) - NCint NCcl(f^{-1}(W))$. Because f is $NC\alpha$ -open.

Theorem 3. 6

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\beta$ -cont. and NC -open function, Then the following statements hold.

- (i) The inverse image of each NC -preopen in Y is $NC\beta$ -open in X .
- (ii) The inverse image of each NC -semiopen in Y is $NC\beta$ -open in X .

Proof. (i) Let $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle \in NC\text{-preopen}(Y)$, $A \subseteq NCint\ NCcl\ A$, then $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(A))) \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(NCcl\ f(A))) \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(A) = NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(A)$.

(ii) Let $D \in NC\text{-semiopen}(Y)$, $D \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ D$, and so, $f^{-1}(D) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl\ NCint\ D) \subseteq NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint(D))) \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint(D))) = NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(NCint(D)) \subseteq NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(D)$.

Theorem 3.7

Let $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ surjective such that $NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ f^{-1}(V) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl\ V)$, for each $NC\text{-open}$ set $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$. if X is connected, then Y is connected.

Proof. Let Y is not connected, i.e., there exists two $NC\text{-open}$ sets V_1 and V_2 such that $V_1 \cup V_2 = Y$ and $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$. Since f is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ then $f^{-1}(V_i) \subseteq (NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(V_i))) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCcl(V_i)) = f^{-1}(V_i)$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$. so, $\cap f^{-1}(V_i) \subseteq \cap NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(V_i)) \subseteq \cap f^{-1}(NCcl(V_i)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\cap V_i) = f^{-1}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$, and $\cup f^{-1}(V_i) \subseteq \cup (NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl(f^{-1}(V_i))) \subseteq \cup f^{-1}(NCcl(V_i)) = \cup f^{-1}(V_i) = f^{-1}(\cup V_i) = f^{-1}(Y) = X$.

Therefore X is not connected which leads to a contradiction. Then Y is connected. The relation between $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ and $\theta\text{-cont.}$ will be clear by the following theorem.

Remark 3.1

The composition of two $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ functions need not be $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ in general, as shown by the following example.

Example 3.3

Let $X=Z=\{a,b,c,d\}$ and $Y=\{a,b,c,d,e\}$ with $NC\text{-topologies}$ $\Gamma_x = \{X_N, \Phi_N, A\}$, $\Gamma_y = \{Y_N, \Phi_N, C\}$, $\Gamma_z = \{Z_N, \Phi_N, D\}$ where $A = \{\{a,b\}, \{c\}, \{b\}\}$, $C = \{\{d\}, \{c\}, \{a,b\}\}$, and $D = \{\{a,d\}, \{c,d\}, \{a,b\}\}$.

Let the identity function $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ and $i: (X, \Gamma_2) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_3)$ defined as $f(a)=a$, $f(b)=b=f(d)$ and $f(c)=e$. it is clear that each of f and i is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ but $f \circ i$ is not $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$

The next theorem shown that under what condition that composition is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$

Theorem 3.8

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ and $g: (Y, \Gamma_2) \rightarrow (Z, \Gamma_3)$ be two functions, if f is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ and $NC\alpha\text{-open}$ and g is a $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$, then $g \circ f$ is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$

Proof. Let $V \subseteq Z$ be a $NC\text{-open}$ set, then $(g \circ f)^{-1}(V) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$, but $g^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$ for g is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$, and by Theorem 2.6, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V)) \in NC\beta(x)$.

Therefore $g \circ f$ is $NC\beta\text{-cont.}$ The following lemma is very useful in the sequel.

Lemma 3.1

If $U = \langle U_1, U_2, U_3 \rangle \in NC\alpha(x)$ and $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \in NC\beta(x)$, then $U \cap V \in NC\beta(u)$.

Proof. Since $U \cap V \subseteq NCint\ NCcl\ NCint\ U \cap NCcl\ NCint\ NCcl\ V \subseteq NCcl\ (NCint\ NCcl\ NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V) \subseteq NCcl\ (NCcl\ NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V) \subseteq NCcl\ (NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V) \cup U = NCcl\ (NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V)$. but $NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V \subseteq U$ is $NC\text{-open}$ in X , then $NCint\ (NCint\ U \cap NCint\ NCcl\ V) \subseteq U$.

$NCclV = NCint U \cap NCint NCclV$, thus $U \cap V \subseteq NCcl (NCint(NCintU \cap NCclV)) \subseteq NCcl(NCint (NCcl (NCintU \cap V) \cap U)) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl (U \cap V) \cap U)) = NCcl(NCint(NCcl(U \cap V) \cap U))$.

Therefore $U \cap V \in (u)$.

Theorem 3.9

If $(, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\beta$ -cont. and $NC\alpha(x)$. Then $f \setminus U$ is $NC\beta$ -cont.

Proof. Let $V = \langle V_{1,2}, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ be a NC -open set, then $f^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$, since $U = \langle U_1, U_2, U_3 \rangle \in NC\alpha(x)$, by Lemma 2.12 $U \cap f^{-1}(V) = (f \setminus U)^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$ therefore $f \setminus U$ is $NC\beta$ -cont.

Lemma 3.2

Let $A = \langle A_{1,2}, A_3 \rangle \subseteq Y \subseteq X$, $Y \in NC\beta(x)$ and $A \in NC\beta(y)$, then $A \in NC\beta(x)$.

Proof. Since $A = \langle A_{1,2}, A_3 \rangle \subseteq NC\beta(y) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(A))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(AUY))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(A)))$. since $NCint NCclA$ is NC -open in Y , then exists a NC -open set $U \subseteq X$ such that $NCint NCclA = U \cap Y$, thus $A \subseteq NCcl(U \cap NCcl NCint NCclY) \subseteq NCcl(NCcl NCint NCcl(U \cap Y)) = NCcl(NCcl NCint NCcl(NCint NCclA)) \subseteq NCcl(NCcl NCint NCclA) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCclA = NCcl NCint NCclA$. Therefore, $A \in NC\beta(x)$.

Theorem 3.10

If $(, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a function, and $\{U_i, i \in I\}$ be a cover of X by $NC\beta$ -open set of X , then f is $NC\beta$ -cont. if $(f \setminus U)$ is $NC\beta$ -cont. for each $i \in I$.

Proof

Let $\langle V_{1,2}, V_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ be a NC -open set, then $(f \setminus U)^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(U_i)$ since $U_i \in NC\beta(x)$. by Lemma 2.12, $(f \setminus U)^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$ for each $i \in I$. but $f^{-1}(V) = \cup (f \setminus U_i)^{-1}(V)$, by Remark 2.9 $f^{-1}(V) \in NC\beta(x)$. this implies that f is $NC\beta$ -cont.

4. Neutrosophic crisp β -open (closed) function.

Definition 4.1

A function $(, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is said to be $NC\beta$ -open If the image of any NC -open set in X is $NC\beta$ -open in Y .

Definition 4.2

A function $(, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is said to be $NC\beta$ -closed If the image of any NC -closed set in X is $NC\beta$ -closed set in Y .

The implications between $NC\beta$ -open ($NC\beta$ -closed) function and other types of NC -open (NC -closed) function are given by the following diagram.

The converses of these statements may be not necessarily true, as shown by the following examples.

Example 4.1

Let $X=Y=\{a,b,c,d\}$ with NC -topologies $\Gamma_x=\{X_N, \Phi_N, A\}$ and Γ_y be an indiscrete NCT .

Where $A=\{\{a,b\}, \{c\}, \{b\}\}$.

The identity function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is $NC\beta$ -open ($NC\beta$ -closed) but not may be NC -semiopen (NC -semiclosed).

Example 4.2

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $Y = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ with NC -topologies $\Gamma_x = \{X_N, \Phi_N, A\}$, $\Gamma_y = \{Y_N, \Phi_N, D\}$. where $A = \{\{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{b, d\}\}$, $D = \{\{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a\}\}$.

A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ defined as $f(a) = b$, $f(b) = d$ and $f(c) = e = f(d)$, it is clear that f is $NC\beta$ -open ($NC\beta$ -closed) but not NC -preopen (NC -preclosed).

Remark 4.1

A one to one function is $NC\beta$ -open iff it is $NC\beta$ -closed.

The following theorem gives easy characterization of a $NC\beta$ -open function.

Theorem 4.1

Let $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a function. The following statements may be equivalent.

- (i) f is $NC\beta$ -open.
- (ii) For each $x \in X$ and U each neighborhood U of X , there exists a $NC\beta$ -open set $W = \langle W_1, W_{2,3} \rangle \subseteq Y$ containing $f(x)$ such that $W \subseteq f(U)$.

Proof. (i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii). Let $x \in X$ and U be a neighborhood U of X , then there exists a NC -open set $V = \langle V_1, V_2, V_3 \rangle \subseteq X$ such that $x \in V \subseteq U$. NC -set $W = f(V)$, since f is $NC\beta$ -open, $f(V) = W \in NC\beta(Y)$ and so $f(x) \in W \subseteq f(U)$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (i). Following directly from the Definition 3.1

Theorem 4.2

Let $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a function. The following statement may be equivalent.

- (i) f is $NC\beta$ -open.
- (ii) $NCint NCcl NCint A \subseteq NC(f^{-1}(A))$; for each $A \subseteq Y$.
- (iii) if f is bijective, $NCint NCcl NCint(f(D)) \subseteq f(NCcl(D))$; for each $D \subseteq X$.

Proof. (i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii). Since f is $NC\beta$ -open and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$, then $NCcl(f^{-1}(A)) \subseteq X$ containing $f^{-1}(A) = \langle f^{-1}(A_1), f^{-1}(A_2), f^{-1}(A_3) \rangle$ by Theorem 3.9 there is a $NC\beta$ -closed set $W = \langle W_1, W_2, W_3 \rangle \supseteq A$ such that $NCcl(f^{-1}(A)) \supseteq f^{-1}(W) \supseteq NCint NCcl NCint f^{-1}(W) \supseteq f^{-1}(NCint NCcl NCint(A))$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii). Let $D \subseteq X$, $(D) \subseteq Y$. NC -set $A = f(D)$ in (ii), then $f^{-1}(NCint NCcl NCint(f(D))) \subseteq NCcl(f^{-1}(f(D))) \subseteq NCcl(D)$ and so, $NCint NCcl NCint(f(D)) \subseteq f(NCcl(D))$.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (i). Suppose $U = \langle U_1, U_2, U_3 \rangle$ is a NC -open set in X , then $NCcl(f(X-U)) = f(X-U) \supseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f(X-U))$. Since f is bijective, $(U) \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f(U))$ i.e., $f(U) \in NC\beta(Y)$, hence f is $NC\beta$ -open. Now we try to construct some new connection between $NC\beta$ -open ($NC\beta$ -closed) functions and other types of NC -open (NC -closed) functions.

Theorem 4.3

Let $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\beta$ -open ($NC\beta$ -closed) function if $W = \langle W_1, W_2, W_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ and $F = \langle F_1, F_2, F_3 \rangle \subseteq X$ is a NC -open (NC -closed) set containing $f^{-1}(W)$, then there exists $NC\beta$ -closed ($NC\beta$ -open) $H = \langle H_1, H_2, H_3 \rangle \subseteq Y$ containing W such that $f^{-1}(H) \subseteq F$.

Proof. $H = \langle H_1, H_2, H_3 \rangle = Y - f(X - F)$, since $f^{-1}(W) \subseteq F$, $W \subseteq H$, hence H is $NC\beta$ -closed and $f^{-1}(H) = X - f^{-1}(f(X - F)) \subseteq F$. the second side of the theorem can be prove by the same manner.

Theorem 4.4

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\alpha$ -cont and $NC\beta$ -open function, Then the inverse image of any $NC\alpha$ -open set in Y is $NC\alpha$ -open set of X .

Proof. Let V be a $NC\alpha$ -open set of Y . so, $A \in NC\beta(x)$, $A \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(A)$ and so, $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCint NCcl NCint(V)) \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(NCint NCcl NCint(V)))$. Since f is $NC\beta$ -open by Theorem 3.7.(ii) we have $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(NCint NCcl NCint(V))) \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint(V)))) \subseteq NCint NCcl f^{-1}(NCint(V))$. Since f is NC -acont., $f^{-1}(V) \subseteq NCint NCcl(f^{-1}(NCint(V))) \subseteq NCint NCcl(NCint NCcl NCint f^{-1}(NCint(V))) \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(f^{-1}(V))$. Hence $f^{-1}(V)$ is a $NC\alpha$ -open set of X .

Corollary 4.1

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\alpha$ -cont. and $NC\beta$ -open function, Then the inverse image of any $NC\alpha$ -closed set in Y is $NC\alpha$ -closed set of X .

Proof. Obvious.

Theorem 4.5

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\alpha$ -cont. and $NC\beta$ -open function, Then the image of any $NC\beta$ -open set in X may be $NC\beta$ -open set of Y .

Proof. Let $A \in NC\beta(x)$, $A \subseteq NCint NCcl NCint(A)$ and so, $f(A) \subseteq f(NCcl NCint NCcl(A)) \subseteq NCcl(f(NCint NCcl(A))) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl (f(NCint NCcl(A))) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl (f(NCcl(A))) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl f(A) = NCcl NCint NCcl f(A)$.

Corollary 4.2

If $f: (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ be a $NC\alpha$ -cont. and $NC\beta$ -open and injective, Then the image of each $NC\beta$ -closed set in X may be it is $NC\beta$ -closed set of Y .

Proof. Let $D \subseteq X$ be $NC\beta$ -closed, then $(X - D) \in NC\beta(x)$ by Theorem 3.8 $(X - D) \subseteq NCcl NCint NCcl (f(X - D))$, $Y - f(D) \subseteq Y - NCcl NCint NCcl (f(D))$. So, $(D) \supseteq NCint NCcl NCint (f(D))$.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce both the neutrosophic crisp nearly continuous functions, the neutrosophic crisp nearly open functions, and we present properties related to them. This paper, will promote the future study on

neutrosophic crisp topological functions and many other general frameworks.

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